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PHASE TRANSFER CATALYSIS: A GREEN METHODOLOGY FOR NEW DRUG DISCOVERY RESEARCH: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The major advances in Green Chemistry, especially Industrial Green Chemistry, over the past decade have been in the area of catalysts. One of such techniques is Phase Transfer Catalysis. The use of a Phase Transfer Catalyst (PTC), which Permits or accelerates the reaction between chemical species situated in different phases to overcome the various problems encountered in synthesis. The reaction in organic synthesis can be achieved under solid – liquid PTC and microwaves irradiation in the absence of solvent, generally under normal pressure in open vessel. Therefore, the review presents a brief introduction to PTC and PTC in the generation of compound libraries of over last few years.

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INTRODUCTION

Green Chemistry has brought about a great revolution today having applications in many fields. It is an environmentally benign chemical synthesis which ensures generation of none or minimum by-products which have no effect on the environment and their disposal is convenient. It includes various techniques like Microwave Assisted Organic Synthesis, Phase Transfer Catalysis, etc. Some of the major advances in Green Chemistry, especially Industrial Green Chemistry, over the past decade have been in the area of catalysts. Through the use of catalysts, chemists have found ways of removing the need for large quantities of reagents that would otherwise have been needed to carry out the transformations and ultimately would have contributed to the waste stream.

Phase Transfer Catalysis (PTC)

Synthesis and production of most of the pharmaceuticals and bulk drugs results in the generation of waste materials, effluents, etc., the disposal of which causes problems and also environmental pollution. One of the most general and efficient methodologies that take care of these problems is to use a Phase Transfer Catalyst (PTC). Difficulties are often encountered in organic synthesis if the organic compound is soluble in organic solvent and the reagent in water. In such cases, the two reactants will react very slowly and the reaction proceeds only at the interface where these two solutions are in contact. The rate of the reaction can be slightly increased by stirring the reaction mixture and by using aprotic polar solvents, which solvate the cations so that the anions are free. Such solvents are expensive and their removal is difficult. Also the use of strong bases causes many side effects to take place. These problems can be overcome by using a PTC, which is soluble in water as well as in the organic solvent [1, 2, 3]. The PTC foundations were laid in the mid to late 1960's by M. Makosza, C.M. Starks, and A. Brandström.⁴ By the time the first non-patent reports of Starks' work appeared, [4,5,6] he had termed the process "Phase Transfer Catalysis" and this name has been widely adopted and is in general use.

Mechanism of Phase Transfer Catalysis (PTC)

The PTC mechanism involves an organic phase containing a substrate and an aqueous phase containing salt of an anionic reagent (often a nucleophile or base).

Because the salt-containing phase is insoluble in the substrate-containing phase, a phase transfer catalyst (usually a quaternary 'onium' salt) is added to the mixture. The lipophilic cation of the catalyst is soluble in both aqueous and organic phases and when in contact with the aqueous phase, exchanges anions with the excess of anion in the salt solution. The anion exchange is given as:

The anion, which will function as nucleophile is paired with Q^+ and finds its way into the organic solution. This may be given by a second phase transfer equilibrium:

Once the nucleophile or base (Nu) is in solution in nonpolar (organic) media, the displacement or deprotonation can take place with product formation. In the case of a nucleophile displacement reaction, Q^+ would be ion-paired with the nucleofuge. The new salt QX generated returns to the aqueous phase, where Q^+ picks up a new Nu⁻ ion for the next cycle. [4]

Starks' Phase Transfer Catalytic Cycle

Advantages of PTC [2]

1. PTC offers significant advantages over conventional procedures
2. Enhancing Productivity
3. Enhancing Environmental Performance and Pollution Prevention
4. Enhancing Safety
5. Reducing raw materials' cost
6. Enhancing Quality
7. Improve Selectivity.

Types of Catalysts

The catalyst will form ion pair, which should be soluble in the organic phase.

Three major families of PTC's are used:

1. Quaternary 'onium' salts.
2. Crown ethers.
3. Cryptands and Podands.

Quaternary 'Onium' Salts:

Quaternary 'onium' salts such as ammonium, phosphonium, antimonium and tert-iary sulphonium salts are available. In practice, however, only a limited number of ammonium and phosphonium salts are widely used.

Quaternary ammonium salts of the general formula, $R_4N^+X^-$, where R is alkyl, aryl or aralkyl group and X is anion are used.⁷ The R groups may or may not be identical.

The general preparation of these salts consists in adding appropriate alkyl halide or sulphate or appropriate leaving group to primary, secondary or tertiary amines.

Many of these salts are crystalline solids at room temperature while few salts are liquids. [5,8,9] Low molecular weight salts upto C_6 -salts are highly soluble in water, but above that the solubility in water rapidly decreases. The formation of ether linkages in one or more of the alkyl groups leads to considerable increase in the water solubility. Polar organic solvents, generally, dissolve quaternary ammonium salts. Physical properties like melting points of the quaternary ammonium salts depend on the nature of anion, symmetry of cation, molecular weight, etc. Thermal stabilities of the catalysts are dependent upon the nucleophilicity of the anion. Quaternary phosphonium salts have greater thermal stability than quaternary ammonium salts.

Some of the quaternary 'onium' salts normally used are:

Aliquat 336: Methyl trioctyl ammonium chloride, $N^+CH_3(C_8H_{17})_3Cl^-$

Benzyl trimethyl chloride or bromide (TMBA), $N^+(CH_3)_3CH_2C_6H_5X^-$ (X=Cl or Br)

Benzyl triethyl ammonium chloride or bromide (TEBA), $N^+(C_2H_5)_3CH_2C_6H_5X^-$ (X=Cl or Br)

Tetra-n-butyl ammonium chloride, bromide, chlorate or hydroxide, $N^+(n-Bu)_4X^-$ (X=Cl, Br, ClO_4 , OH)

Crown Ethers:

Crown Ethers are macrocyclic polyethers having unique properties such as: Specific complexations of metal salts, ionic or neutral organic or inorganic molecules. Ability to transfer ionic reagents from aqueous or solid phase to organic phase. *e.g.* 18-Crown-6(18-C-6) and Dibenzo-18-Crown-6(DB-18-C-6) are 18 membered heterocyclic rings containing 6 oxygen atoms as complex forming ligands. The cavity diameter of 18-C-6 and DB-18-C-6 are estimated to be 2.6-3.2 Å which is ideal for complexing with a potassium or sodium cation. This macrocyclic multidentate ligand will also effectively complex with other alkyl metal cations.

Mechanism:

The principle upon which the crown ethers work is complexation. [10]

The non-bonding electrons of the 6 oxygen atoms of typical crown ether (*e.g.* 18-C-6, Dibenzo-18-Crown-6) are able to make a complex with the metal cation, which very well fits into the cavity of the crown ether. Metal cation (M^+ *e.g.* Na^+) is thus made free from its counter anionic part. The positive charge is distributed to entire crown ether molecule and the counter anion X^- (*e.g.* CN^-) remains attached to the crown ether molecule through the electrostatic forces. Since the crown ether molecule has organophilic outer covering, the crown ether molecule along with the complexed metal cation and the counter anion *i.e.* crown M^+X^- becomes more organic soluble than uncomplexed M^+X^- salt.

Mechanism Of Solubilisation**Cryptands and Podands:**

These are Third Generation Catalysts used as PTC's.

Cryptands are a family of synthetic bi- and polycyclic multidentate ligands for a variety of cations. The term 'Cryptands' implies that this ligand binds substrates in a crypt. These molecules are 3-D analogues of crown ethers but are more selective and complex the guest ions more strongly. The resulting complexes are lipophilic. Many Cryptands are commercially available under the trade name "Kryptofix". The 3-D interior cavity of a cryptand provides a binding site or hook for "guest" ions. The complex between the cationic guest and the cryptand is called as a crypt ate. Cryptands form complexes with many "hard cations" including NH_4^+ , lanthanides, alkali metals and alkaline earth metals. In contrast to typical crown ethers, cryptands bind the guest ions using both nitrogen and oxygen donors. Their 3-D encapsulation mode confers some size selectivity enabling discrimination among alkyl metal cations (*e.g.* Na^+ vs. K^+). Cryptands, although they are more expensive and more difficult to prepare, offer much better selectivity and strength of binding than other complexants for alkyl metals, such as crown ethers.

PTC AND MICROWAVE IRRADIATION IN ORGANIC SYNTHESIS [11,12]

Numerous reactions in organic synthesis can be achieved under solid-liquid PTC and microwaves irradiation in the absence of solvent, generally under normal pressure in open vessel. Since microwave activation is rather recent technique, the number of examples can be appear limited at the present time, but is rapidly extending.

O-Alkylations

In conventional methods, PTC has provided interesting examples for alkylation. Coupling with microwave activation has proved to be quite fruitful.

ESTERS SYNTHESIS:

Alkyl Acetates

Potassium acetate can be readily alkylated in a domestic oven using equivalent amounts of salt and alkylating agents in presence of Aliquat 336 (10% mol.) Some main result, as exemplified for are given in Table-1

Table-1: Alkylation of CH₃COOK under microwave (Domestic oven, 600W).

RX	Time (min.)	Final temp. (°C)	Yield (%)
n-C ₈ H ₁₇ Br	1	187	98
n-C ₈ H ₁₇ Cl	1	162	98
n-C ₈ H ₁₇ I	2	165	92
n-C ₁₆ H ₃₃ Br	1	169	98

Yields are practically equivalent within 1-2 min. in all the cases, regardless of the chain length, nature of halide leaving group, and reagent amount.

Long Chain Esters

As a generalization of the above method, stearyl stearate was synthesized within 1 min. in a quantitative yield.

Aromatic Esters

It is possible to perform the alkylation of aromatic acids directly without the necessity of preparing the reactive potassium salt in a discrete step, since it can be generated in situ by reacting the acid with a base (potassium hydroxide or carbonate) in the presence of phase transfer catalyst

Aliquat (10%)

Aliquat (10%)

A striking case in this series deals with terephthalic acid alkylation. This specific effect of microwave irradiation appears clearly in this example, since other factors being equal, the yield are unambiguously much higher.

	Time	Temp	Yield
MW (600 W)	7 min	227 °C	87%
Classical heating	7 min.	227 °C	20%

ETHER SYNTHESIS:

Aliphatic Ethers

Two types of condition were studied for this reaction by Yuan *et al.* using either the alcohols or their corresponding halides as starting materials. In the presence of quaternary ammonium salts, the reaction shown in given equation is completed within a few minutes. Typical results are given in following table

Furanic Diether

A new family of furanic diether was obtained by the alkylation of 2,5-furandimethanol or furfuryl alcohol, using microwave and PTC solvent-free conditions.

	Time	Temp	Yield
Microwave monomode reactor (30W)	5 min	180 °C	93%
Conventional heating (oil-bath)	5min	80 °C	41%

Phenolic Ethers

As compounds of biological interest, the preparation of gram quantities of aryl-2-(N,N-diethylamino) ethyl ethers was described in a conventional microwave oven using KOH and glyme as the transfer agent,

	Time	Temp	Yield
Microwave monomode reactor (600W)	2 min	180 °C	92-99%

Under microwave irradiation, a number of phenols react remarkably fast in dry media with a number of primary alkyl halides to give aromatic ethers.

Y	R-X	Time	Yield
H	PhCH ₂ Cl	50 sec	78%
p-NH ₂	Me ₂ SO ₄	25 sec	87%
H	PhCH ₂ Cl	4 sec	89%

The syntheses of 8-quinolyl ethers from 8-hydroxyquinolines and organic halides has also been reported under PTC condition and microwaves,

MW(750 W) 3-15 min.			
Y	R-X	Time	Yield
H	PhCH ₂ Cl	7 min	87%
H	PhCOCH ₂ Br	13 min	91%

Phenolic polyethers

Polycondensation of 3,3-bis(chloromethyl)oxetane and various bisphenols were studied using the microwave PTC technique. The results obtained show the advantage of microwave fields in terms of molecular weight for crystalline polymer as reflected in higher values of transition temperature and melting point and also in reaction times for all types of reaction times and all types of structures.

N-Alkylation

Saccharin

Rapid N-alkylation of saccharin by a series of halides was performed on silica gel via its sodium salt in a microwave oven. TEBA was shown to provide a useful, co-catalytic effect.

Benzoxazinones and Benzothiazinones were performed under PTC and microwaves as well as Michael reactions using the same condition.

Barbitone

Acetanilide

The N-alkylation of acetanilide under microwave irradiation in the presence of PTC has been reported.

Phthalimide: Gabriel reaction

Azaheterocycles

A number of azaheterocycles (*i.e.*, pyrrole, imidazole, indole and carbazole) reacts remarkably fast with alkyl halides to give exclusively N-alkyl derivatives.

C-alkylation of Active Methylenes

Several monoalkylations of functionalized acetates have been described in a series of Chinese. Significant results are given. Rapid monoalkylation are achieved in good yield when compared with classical ways. Of particular interest is the synthesis of alpha-amino acids *via* alkylation of aldimines under microwave activation. Subsequent acidic hydrolysis of the alkylated imine provides leucine, serine or phenylalanine in preparatively useful yields within 1-5 minutes.

Nucleophilic addition to Carbonyl compounds

Aldol condensation

Jasminaldehyde was obtained classically from heptanol and benzaldehyde in 70 % yield over 3 days at room temperature, by using a 600 W domestic microwave oven, an enhanced yield of 82 % was achieved within only 1 minute. The amount of side product decreased from 30% to 18% using this technique.

Ester Saponification

Esters are easily saponified in a few minutes using powdered potassium hydroxide (2 mol equi.) and Aliquat (10 %) in the absence of solvent

Three important conclusions:

1. Rapid and easy reaction occurs, even with the most hindered mesitoic esters, which are otherwise practically non-specifiable under classical conditions.
2. The advantage of using a monomode reactor versus a domestic oven appears clearly.
3. More interesting from a fundamental viewpoint is the very strong specific.

Base	Ultrasound Cond.			Microwave Cond.			Classical Heat		
	Time (Hr)	Temp ⁰ C	Yield(%)	Time(Hr)	Temp ⁰ C	Yield (%)	Time(Hr)	Temp ⁰ C	Yield (%)
KOH,TABA	1	75	81	10	130	81	--	--	--
t-BuOK,TBAB	1	35	70	5	75	87	5	75	36
KOH,TABA	1	75	81	10	65	28	--	--	--
t-BuOK,TBAB	1	45	70	5	60	95	5	64	41

Base Catalyzed Transesterification

Transesterification occur readily in microwaves ovens due to the displacement of the equilibrium by the evaporation of polar volatile compounds

This study was next extended to the synthesis of benzoyl and dodecanoyl derivatives from protected carbohydrates. Microwaves assisted PTC transesterification with methylbenzoate or dodecanoate were thus studied for several carbohydrates .Small amount of DMF were shown to be necessary to provide good yield (76-96%) within 15 minutes Rate enhancement when compared to conventional heating and specific microwave activation were especially noticeably when less reactive fatty compounds were involves.

Deprotonations

Base catalyzed isomerization of allylic Aromatic compounds

Eugenol is a natural product available from a variety of essential oils. Its isomerization into isoeugenol, the starting materials for synthetic vanillin, is rather difficult and proceeds in modest yield under relatively harsh condition .It can be very efficiently prepared however using 2.2 molar equivalents of base and catalytic (5%) amounts of Aliquat in the absence of solvent.

Carbene Generation (α -elimination)

Dichlorocarbene was generated under solid-liquid conditions using microwaves .Refluxing a mixture of CHCl_3 powdered NaOH and trace amounts of CTAB in cyclohexene under microwave irradiation provided 90% of dichlorononcarone within 20 min. ,versus 81 % in 60 min. without microwave exposure or only 12 % in 90 min. without catalyst.

β -elimination

Bromo acetals in acidic media can lead to cyclic ketene acetals. These B-eliminations Previously performed under solid-liquid PTC without and with sonication, were further improved by microwave irradiation. β -elimination on bromo acetals In a reactor (75 W)

Miscellaneous Reactions

Nucleophilic aromatic substitution

The irradiation of a mixture of ortho or para nitrochlorobenzene and ethanol in the presence of sodium hydroxide and a PTC agent yields the corresponding ethoxy aromatic compounds within a few minutes .The same procedure was subsequently applied to 2-chlorophenol. In the both cases, PEG 400 was shown to be most effective catalyst.

Nucleophilic aromatic substitution under microwave 420-700			
Z	Catalyst	Time (min.)	Yield (%)
4-NO ₂	none	2	14
	PhCH ₂ NMe ₃ Cl	2	51
	PEG 400	2	99
2-NO ₂	PEG 400	2	99
	PhCH ₂ NMe ₃ Cl	2	70
2-OH	PEG 400	2	82

Dealoxycarbonylation of Activated Esters (Krapcho reaction)

This type of reaction is usually best performed in DMSO solution. A simpler procedure was proposed using anionic activation and microwave irradiation, with a metal salt as the reagent and a PTC in the absence of solvent. This procedure was applied to the striking case of β -ketoesters and considerable improvements can be noted when the maximum yield obtained under classical Krapcho condition.

De alkoxylation carbonylation of cyclic β -ketoester in a monomode reactor.

R	Time (min.)	Power (W)	Temp. degree C	Yield
H	8	30	138	96
Et	15	45	160	94
n-Bu	20	45	167	89
n-Hex	20	90	186	87

In order to verify the specific effects of microwave irradiations, the second experiment [R=Et] was performed using conventional oil bath heating under the same conditions of time and temperature [15 min, 160^o C]. No reaction was observed. Further heating for three hours led to total conversion but the yield [60] was limited by product degradation. Clearly, when compared to conventional heating, microwave heating provides a large reduction in time, simplified experimental conditions, and the prevention of product degradation at high temperature.

[1, 3]-dipolar cycloaddition of Diphenylnitrilimine

Diphenylnitrilimine (DPNI) can be subjected to 1, 3-dipolar cycloaddition with activated double bonds as dipolarphiles. It can be generated in situ by the reaction of hydrazonyl chloride with a base. The cycloaddition can be performed almost quantitatively within 6 min. microwaves irradiation using KF and Aliquat as a base. For the sake of illustration, result with substituted chalcones indicated in given table. When the same reactions are performed all other factors being equal (time, Temperature), no reaction occurs under classical thermal conditions. This behaviour once more confirms a specific radiation effect.

1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of DPNI to chalcones in a monomode reactor (30 W).

R	Time (min.)	Temp. degree C	Yield %
H	6	170	90
Br	5	170	93
Cl	6	174	95
Me	6	168	87
OMe	6	175	89

β -Lactams Synthesis

Silyl ketene acetals with aldimines to give β -lactams using KF in the presence of a PTC (18-crown ether) within a few minutes using microwave irradiation in close Teflon vessels.

Selective Dealkylations of Aromatic Ethers

Ethyl isoeugenol and ethoxy anisole can be selectively demethylated or deethylated using potassium t-butoxide in the presence of 18-crown-6. Under solvent free conditions only ethylation is observed whereas, in the presence of ethylene glycol, the selectivity is totally reversed and demethylation becomes the major process. In both cases, considerable increase in reaction rate were observed under microwave irradiation when compared to classical heating [13].

Phase transfer catalyzed synthesis of 1- Aryloxyacetyl-4-(2-methylphenoxy acetyl)- thiosemicarbazides under microwave irradiation[14]

Aryloxyacetyl-4-(2-methylphenoxy acetyl)- thiosemicarbazides (3a-1) are synthesized via reaction of 2-methylphenoxyacetyl chloride with ammonium thiocyanate & aryloxyacetic acid hydrazides (2a-1) using polyethylene glycol -400 as catalyst under 600w microwave irradiation for 9 min.

3	Ar	3	Ar
A	C ₆ H ₅	G	4-ClC ₆ H ₄
B	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	H	1-Naphthyl
C	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	I	2-Naphthyl
D	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	J	2-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄
E	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	K	3-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄
F	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	l	4-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄

Microwave promoted efficient Synthesis of N-Aryl-N-aryl thioureas under solvent –free & phase transfer catalysis conditions[15].

Synthesis of compounds under solvent free & microwave irradiation condition. Reaction between benzoyl chloride & potassium isothiocyanate under solvent free & microwave irradiation condition. These steps are solid –liquid phase reaction though solvents free condition . Here carried out two experiments with PTC & Without PTC.

Table: N-Aryl-N-aryl thioureas 2a-m prepared.

Entry	R	M.P./ ^o C	Lit.M.P./ ^o C	Yield %
2a	C ₆ H ₅	147-148	148	98
2b	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	127-128	128	95.9
2c	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	158-159	157	91.9
2d	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	140-141	139	89.4
2e	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	164-165	164	86.1
2f	2-Cl C ₆ H ₄	143-144	144	95
2g	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	139-140	140.5	98.1
2h	4-Br C ₆ H ₄	149-150	150	95.8
2i	4-F C ₆ H ₄	127-128	128-129.5	97.1
2j	1-Nephthyl	168-170	171	94.8
2k	2-Nephthyl	171-172	173	85.1
2l	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	116-117	117	95.6
2m	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	154-155	154.4-155	94.9

Synergism of low energy microwave irradiation & solide-liquid phase transfer catalyst for selective alkylation of phenols to phenolic ethers[16].

General synthesis of phenolic ethers using microwave irradiated S-L PTC (MISL-PTC) under low energy input using tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) as catalyst in presence of NaOH at 90^oC .Benzyl chloride was used as an alkylating agent. In each alkylation process, phenyl ethers were produced with 100% selective in MISL-PTC vis –a-vis MILL-PTC. The rate of the reaction increased significantly under microwave irradiation as compared with the conventional heating under otherwise similar conditions

Novelties of microwave assisted liquid-liquid phase transfer catalysis in enhancement of rates & selectives in alkylation of phenols under mild conditions[17].

The report of general synthesis of phenolic ethers using microwaves under low energy input using tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB) as phase transfer catalyast in presence of NaOH as base at 90⁰C. The generalized reaction is shown in a scheme-22 (R¹=substitutent, R=Nucleophile).

No	Substrate	Conventional heating			Microwave heating		
		10min (%)	3h (%)	Selectivity (0-alkylated product) after 3h	10min (%)	3h (%)	Selectivity (0-alkylated product) after 3h
1		6.1	82.2	92.5(76)	10.9	86	92.6
2		10	81	96.2(78)	17	86	95.6
3		7	79	86(68)	11	82	87.2
4		2	64	90.2(58)	18	71	92.3
5		4	84	99.8(84)	14	91	99.9
6		3	58	99(57)	10	68	97.3
7		4	84	89.6(75)	24	85	98.8
8		10	86	89.4(77)	31	91	89.6
9		11	83	93.7(78)	25	87	94.6
10		4	87	97.3(85)	19	94	97.8

Palladium and phase transfer catalyzed Heck Cross coupling reaction in water under microwave irradiation [18]

Palladium-catalyst vinylation of aryl halides in water without organic cosolvent via microwave irradiation under phase transfer conditions gives the trans-stilbenes and substituted trans-cinnamic acid in good high yield.

Table 6.10 Comparison of time and yields on the formation of compounds 3a-3g using microwave and conventional heating.

Product		Conventional Heating		Microwave Heating		t_c / t_{max}		
R	Y	t(min)	Yield (%)	Power(W)	t(min)		Yield (%)	
3a	Ph	Ph	420	85	375	10	91	42
3b	Ph	COOH	180	88	375	10	88	18
3c	<i>p</i> -HO ₂ CC ₆ H ₄	COOMe	420	90	375	10	92	42
3d	<i>p</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	Ph	180	80	375	10	89	18
3e	<i>o</i> -O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	Ph	180	80	375	10	86	18
3f	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	420	84	375	10	89	42
3g	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	COOH	300	54	375	10	93	30

Microwave assisted synthesis of melatonin[19]

Melatonin was prepared from phthalimide by N- and C-alkylation, cyclization, hydrolytic, decarboxylation and acetylation. N-alkylation of phthalimide with 1,3-dibromo-propane in the presence of potassium carbonate and phase-transfer catalyst under the condition of microwave irradiation for just only 6 min, then C-alkylation of ethyl acetate with the resulting bromide at another 6 min gave compound (2) in 81% yield. It condensed and cyclised with 4-methoxyphenyl hydrazine at same microwave irradiation condition for 15 min to get the desired 2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-(2-phthalimidoethyl)-5-methoxyindole (3) in 80% yield through the Fischer indole synthesis. Then through saponification and treatment with the solution of sulfuric acid under microwave irradiation afforded 5-methoxytryptamine (4) in 70% yield. The resulting product was acetylated under microwave irradiation for 2 min to give melatonin in 85% yield. The synthetic route is,

Method	From 1 to 2	Yield (%)	From 2 to 3	Yield (%)	From 3 to 4	Yield (%)	From 4 to 5	Yield (%)
Traditional method	6 hr	85; 77; 72	10-12 hr	74	8 hr	66	1-2 hr	85
Microwave irradiation	6+6 min	81	15 min	80	5+10 min	70	2 min	85

Synthesis of 1, 4-dihydropyridines in water using phase-transfer catalyst under microwave irradiation[20]

The synthesis of various substituted 1,4-dihydropyridines has been achieved by the reaction of aldehydes, ethyl/methyl acetoacetates, and ammonium acetate in water using phase transfer catalyst under microwave irradiation. Compared to the classical Hantzsch's reaction conditions, this new method consistently has the advantage of good yields and short reaction times. Bifunctional compounds containing two units have been synthesized using dialdehyde as precursor in good yields.

Sr.No.	R ₁	R ₂	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	OMe	4a	10	85
2	3-(NO ₂)- C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4b	10	82
3	4-(OMe)- C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4c	10	80
4	4-(Cl)- C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4d	10	88
5	2-Furyl	OMe	4e	5	91
6	2,4-(Cl) ₂ - C ₆ H ₃	OMe	4f	10	77
7	4-(OH)- C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4g	10	81
8	2-(Cl)- C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4h	10	79
9	4-(Me)- C ₆ H ₄	OMe	4i	10	81
10	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	OMe	4j	5	86
11	H	OMe	4k	3	91
12	Me	OMe	4l	10	85
13	n-C ₃ H ₇	OMe	4m	5	86
14	(CH ₃) ₂ CH-CH ₂	OMe	4n	10	81
15	C ₆ H ₅	OEt	4o	10	83
16	3-(NO ₂)- C ₆ H ₄	OEt	4p	10	80
17	2-Furyl	OEt	4q	5	89
18	Me	OEt	4r	10	79
19	H	OEt	4s	3	92
20	Terephthalyl	OEt	4t	10	78
21	Terephthalyl	OMe	4u	10	82

A rapid and efficient synthesis of symmetrical disulfides under PTC-microwave irradiation conditions [21]

A rapid and general method for the synthesis of symmetrical disulfides involves reaction of sulfur with sodium hydroxide under phase transfer catalyst-microwave condition to give sodium disulfide, which reacts with alkyl halides to afford the disulfides in good to excellent isolated yields.

The phase transfer catalyst not only involved in the formation of the disulfide ion in solution, but also catalyses the substitution reaction on the alkyl chlorides.

The impact of the PTC-microwave irradiation and PTC for the synthesis of compounds 3a-I has been compared and results are summarized in following table.

Product		Phase transfer catalysis			Microwave irradiation			t _p /t _{p-mw}
Entry	R	X	t (hr)	Yield (%)	Power (W)	t (min)	Yield (%)	
3a	t-C ₄ H ₉	Cl	4	50	375	6	90	34
3b	n- C ₃ H ₁₁	Cl	4	76	375	6	88	34
3c	CH ₂ =CH-CH ₂	Cl	4	80	375	6	90	34
3d	C ₆ H ₅ =CH ₂	Cl	4	95	375	6	91	34
3e	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	Cl	4	97	375	6	85	34
3f	2-Br C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	Br	4	70	375	6	81	34
3g	4-O ₂ N C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	Br	4	80	375	7	67	40
3h	2-O ₂ N C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂	Br	4	75	375	7	65	40
3i	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ CH ₂	Br	4	90	375	6	90	34

The results show that the synthesis of compounds 3 a-i under PTC-microwave irradiation are 34-40 times faster than under phase transfer condition. This ratio between the reaction time using PTC and PTC-microwave irradiation (t_p/t_{p-mw}), under the same condition, quantities the PTC-MW effect.

Decomposition of sodium trichloroacetate in the presence of quaternary ammonium under microwave irradiation: A convenient one-pot synthesis of α -hydroxyl acids in water [22]

A good yielding phase transfer catalyzed procedure for one pot preparation of α -hydroxy acids from carbonyl compounds and sodium trichloroacetate by in situ addition and hydrolysis under microwave irradiation is described. Decomposition of sodium trichloroacetate is strongly accelerated by the presence of quaternary ammonium. The reaction can be conducted in water. An advantage of this method is that the intermediate α -trichloromethyl carbinols are not isolated. Additionally, the fact that products exist in the water phase facilitates a simple isolation of the desired α -hydroxy acids, although hydrolysis reactions produce a few viscous and fuscous materials.

Entry	Substrate	Conventional heating			Microwave heating		
		Time (min) addition, hydrolysis	Yield (%)	Yield (%)	Time (min) addition, hydrolysis	Yield (%)	Yield (%)
1	Hydrocinnamaldehyde	10	40	70	1.5	5	35
2	Cinnamaldehyde	10	40	20	2	5	12
3	Benzaldehyde	8	30	61	1.5	4	30
4	4-nitrobenzaldehyde	5	30	63	1	3	25
5	4-chlorobenzaldehyde	8	30	63	1.5	4	36
6	4-methoxybenzaldehyde	8	30	71	1.5	4	40
7	3-methylbutaraldehyde	6	335	80	2	5	50
8	<i>n</i> -heptaldehyde	10	40	77	2	5	45
9	Cyclohexanone	12	40	50	2.5	5	40
10	Diphenylketone	10	30	56	2.5	5	41

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